

Comparative Historic Studies of Guinean and Chinese Art

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

This research paper responds to the associated research problem in Art history by making a comparative study between two countries' (Guinea and China) art history. One of the attractive aspects of Africa art is knowing its diversity and the complementary of its natural ecosystems, the intermingling of populations originally from different social and cultural activities and practices and a unique political history explain the exceptional richness of Guinean culture. This richness reflect our love for each other and the union through our different Art and culture which gave us power to stand the value of our art object no matter you ethnics or your beliefs because this art history put us together as one in order to help each one us in need and outsider as well. Chinese art has arguably the oldest continuous tradition in the world, and is marked by an unusual degree of continuity within, and consciousness of, that tradition, lacking an equivalent to the Western collapse and gradual recovery of classical styles. Through our political diplomacy relationship with China (one of the greatest country in Art and cultural history), we have to realize the greatness of the culture as well as their Art history. China has the biggest art history in the all Asia, knowing their ability of reproducing the past into design to remind their future generation about the past of their country history. More than thousand arts objects in their possession which painting, sculpture, poetry and so on. The objects such as Nimba mask, Sosso Bala, for Guinea, jade stone and Pipa for china will be compare through method mention below all so talking about the study purpose which can make clear the goal needed for this project. The opinion of people about this comparative study is analyzing it by using the formal analysis method and comparative method by concluding with the observation.

Keywords: NIMBA MASK, GUINEA, JADE STONE, CHINA, ART

Introduction

Art history doesn't consist of simply listing and placing all the art movements on a timeline. It is the study of art objects considered within the period of their time. At the time they were created, art historians analyze the meaning of the visual arts (painting, sculpture, architecture). Furthermore, another mission of art history is to establish the authorial origins of artworks, to discover who created a work, when and for what reason. Iconography is an integral part of the history of art. It consists of an analysis of the symbolism arts works. For example, art historians identify a painting's visual elements, and interpret its meaning. Art historians are interested in what the artworks represented at the time of their creation. It is a way of learning about past civilizations. Art history help us understand our culture (recounts stories of our past) allows us to look back and understand how our civilization evolved over the centuries. It is a way to know ourselves better. Studying art history is really not about memorizing dates, artists' names, art movements, etc. Instead, it drives you to analyze paintings, photographs, sculptures, etc. To support your analysis and developing your critical thinking, (Guinea museum of Sandervalia, 2012).

Comparative studies are the studies to demonstrate ability to examine, compare and contrast subjects or ideas. Comparative study shows how two subjects are similar or different. When the practice of comparative study began is a matter of debate.

Comparative study research is the act of comparing two or more things with a view to discover something about one or all of the things being compared. This technique often utilizes multiple disciplines in one study. When it comes to method, the majority agreement is that there is no methodology peculiar to comparative research. The multidisciplinary approach is good for the flexibility it offers, yet comparative programs do have a case to answer against the call that their research lacks a seamless whole.

There are certainly methods that are far more common than others in comparative studies, however. Quantitative analysis is much more frequently pursued than qualitative, and this is seen by the majority of comparative studies which use quantitative data. But actually most people are using formal analysis and comparative, The general method of comparing things is the same for comparative research as it is in our everyday practice of comparison. Like cases are treated alike, and different cases are treated differently like the art's one; the extent of difference determines how differently cases are to be treated. Art history is the study of artistic artifacts in a historical and stylistic sense and visual expression. Art history involves the study of artifacts produced in the world and throughout history by various cultures that convey significance, value or serve utility primarily by visual means. This research paper will be based on a comparative study between Guinea art and Chinese's one by emphasizing on two arts objects of each country. Nimba mask and Balafon of Sosso Bala for Guinea and jade culture and shaman mask for china.

Main Objectives

The main objective of this article is to know and make out the differences and similarities between those two countries art history by using some of their objects in the past that I mention above, knowing their powers and

weaknesses, their improvements in social, economic, and cultural context.

Benefits

- The benefit of this comparative study is to see art history in new and different way, making art movement clear and understandable.
- Sharing each other country's art educational system
- Developing Guinea and china art reciprocally by exchanging our art objects through museums.
- This offer help in the education for interested entities to work in other countries and other cultures. They present a fruitful type of study for those who simply wish to learn more about other people and other nations.
- They help the individual win an increased and deeper understand his own viewpoint and his own culture.

Materials and methods

Through the main objectives and the benefits of this project, the identification of those objects is crucial part of this work, because it will help reader know more about them.

Nimba Mask

Nimba mask know as one of the best art sculpture en Africa and also one of the most attractive objects in the Museum of African Arts, also one of the most intriguing, is known by the name of Nimba. This piece was among the first to be aquisited by Veda and Dr Zdravko Pecar for their collection which forms the base of the present-day museum. This headdress is unique in the art of the Africans. It originates among the Baga people living in Guinea, in the most western parts of the African continent. The Nimba was employed in rice harvest dance ceremonies performed in order to procure the fertility of the fields. Nimba is assumed to represent a divinity of abundance and fertility, but the precise interpretation is yet to be obtained. It is also linked with pregnant women, and those wishing to secure their progeny (Museum of African Art, 2020). The dancer carried it on his shoulders, holding the piece by its front legs, while his whole body was adorned in a costume made of vegetal fibers.

Figure 1: Nimba Mask

Jade Stone

Jade stone in Chinese culture is reflected in its status as a symbol of goodness, preciousness and beauty. To the Chinese, jade stone is also the embodiment of the Confucian virtues of courage, wisdom, modesty, justice and compassion. The polish and brilliance of jade stone is considered by the Chinese to be representative of purity while its compactness and hardness reflect intelligence. Justice is represented by its angles and the sound produced by it when it is struck is a symbol of music. The color of jade stone depicts loyalty while its flaws reflect sincerity. [The British Museum, \(2021\)](#), Chinese also value jade stone because of its brightness; representing heaven, while its substance is representative of the earth.

The significance of jade stone to Chinese culture is evident, not only historically, but at present as well. The Chinese term for jade, "yu" is often used in family names as well as in terms that describe people or things that are beautiful, [\(Shoulder helmet mask, 2005\)](#)

Figure 2: Jade Stone

Pipa

It's one of the popular Chinese instrument that has been played for several thousand years made by two syllables pi and pa. It's often found in the hand of heavenly maidens depicted in traditional painting, it's also construct further epitomizes ancient Chinese belief its body by traditional measurement. As stated by [Zeitlin and Kenan, \(2014\)](#) the Pipa has a long history with the Chinese people. Those composition were passed from a master to student over the time. The Chinese Pipa is a four-string plucked lute that originated in West and Central Asia and made its debut in China during the Northern Wei period (386–534). It brought not only a new sound, but also new repertoires and musical theory, as it traveled along historic trade routes. The twisted silk strings were plucked with a big triangular plectrum held in the right hand, and it was originally held horizontally like a guitar. The plectrum's plucking strokes are described by the word Pipa: pi means "to play ahead," while pa means "to play backward." During the Tang dynasty (618–907), musicians started plucking the strings with their fingernails and holding the instrument in a more upright stance.

Figure 3: The Pipa musical instrument

Sosso Bala

The original Sosso-Bala is reportedly preserved in a round mud hut with other sacred and historical objects in the village of Nyagassola in northern Guinea, an area occupied by the Dökala family, the Kouyaté griots of Nyagassola. The 13th-century instrument cannot leave the village unless it is carried on the back of its keeper. It is brought out of its hut once a year for ceremonial playing. Originally owned and played by King Sumaoro Kanté, who succeeded to the Sosso throne in the early thirteenth century, the balafon has transmitted epic poems down through the centuries, principally the Sunjata epic that comprises hymns to the glory of the builder of the Mali Empire. The sacred balafon instrument, known as the Sosso- Bala, has been perceived as the symbol of the freedom and cohesion of the Mandingue community, which is spread across a territory that once belonged to the Empire of Mali. According to [Curtis and Sarro, \(1997\)](#), Originally owned and played by King Sumaoro Kanté, who succeeded to the Sosso throne in the early thirteenth century, the balafon has transmitted epic poems down through the centuries, principally the Sunjata epic that comprises hymns to the glory of the builder of the Mali Empire ([Larson, 2019](#)). The world's oldest balafon, a musical instrument similar to xylophone known as the "Sosso-Bala", has been in existence since the 13th Century. The ancient West African instrument can be found in Nyagassola town on the Mali-Guinea border. The instrument consists of 21 slats made of rosewood. The slats serve as the keys and they are tied together with nylon strings, or sometimes antelope or goatskin. Underneath each key are gourds to amplify the sound while bamboo trees make up the thin base.

Figure 5: Sosso Bala musical instrument

Formal Analysis

This method is quite simply an analysis of the forms utilized in the work of art. It is a close inspection of the artist's use of aspects such as color, shape, line, mass, and space. The formal analysis moves beyond simple description in that it connects the elements of the work to the effects they have on the viewer, Fagg, (1961). Considering this connection enables the writer to discuss the meaning of the work. Begin with a brief but thorough description of the work.

- What is the title?
- Who is the artist?
- What year was it created?
- What is the physical condition of the work? Is it dirty, clean, and restored? Include historical information?
- What country or region was it made in?
- Does it belong to a particular movement, age, or school of thought?
- Does it have an influential patron?
- Is this work typical or atypical of its period, style, or artist?
- How does the art “work?” That is, what details in the piece are used to convey its meaning? Consider how these details function by themselves and together as a whole.

Architecture and Space:

- What is the form of the structure, and what is the function? How do form and function complement each other?
- Is the structure useful? How do people move throughout the structure? Are there significant accommodations or restrictions to this movement?
- Is the building or space structurally sound, given its location, design, and materials?

- What role does daylight play? Is the inside bright or somber?
- Do the exterior and interior complement each other? Is either adorned with ornamentation in the form of statuary, color, or paintings?
- How does the artist use color? Are there stark contrasts or is it blended? Are there symbolic meanings behind the color choices?
 - How does the artist use line? Are forms linearly arranged or disordered? Are there geometric shapes implied by the forms in the piece?
 - Are the forms in the piece realistic or abstract? Are they fully one style or do they mix the two?
- Sculpture and 3-D Pieces:
 - What is the medium of the piece, and how does it affect the viewer's impression? (For example, stone gives a sense of permanence and strength.)
 - What was the purpose of this piece? In what setting was it originally placed?
- Is the piece unusually large or small?
- Is the piece representational or abstract? Is the artist exploring forms or space within forms?
 - Is the piece a portrait of a person? What type of impression does it give of the subject? Is the pose strong or relaxed? Are there objects with the person?

Comparative Analysis

This one starts with a formal analysis of two or more individual pieces, and then adds another level of discussion that evaluates relevant similarities and differences between the pieces. This added level is useful in revealing details about trends within historical periods, regional similarities, or growth of an individual artist over time (MacGregor, 1977).

- In describing the individual pieces, keep to the same conventions used when doing an individual formal analysis.
 - Ask yourself why this comparison is relevant. There is a wealth of information in why your professor has asked for a comparison of two particular pieces.
 - Depending on the length and complexity of comparison, one of the two following basic structures will be more appropriate:
 - “Lumping” involves discussing all details of one work, and then all details of the second work. This method is preferred in lengthy or broad comparisons to avoid zipping back and forth between the works too quickly. Remember to compare the two works by referring back to the first work when discussing the second. This will ensure that you don't simply write two descriptions.
 - “Splitting” involves discussing a particular point in both works before moving on to another point. This method is preferred in comparisons dealing with fine details instead of a broader look at each work as a whole. Remember to discuss each point evenly to maintain a clear, parallel structure.

Result and Discussion

The differences and similarities between these art objects starting by Nimba Mask and Jade Stone then Sosso Bala and Pipa. They are quite similar according to their power, influence and impact in the two different countries culture.

Nimba Mask and Jade Stone

Similarities

They are all symbol of goodness, purification, beauty, justice and compassion, those are behavior they have in common without forgetting their perfectibility protection and chances (Braid, 2021).

Differences

Jade stone is an art object that can be reproduced in so many form and design but their purpose still the same, the color green means a lot which depict loyalty and also reflect sincerity.

As for the Nimba Mask it only represent one culture, the Baga's one. Knowing its power, beauty of the sculpture and its influence on that community, the government decide to value the art object which makes it one of the most attractive in Africa, without denying its implication on the Rice and Harvest, women fecundity and those who wish to secure their progeny.

Figure 6: Green Jade designed in a form of elephant

Sosso Bala and Pipa

Similarities

Sosso Bala and Pipa are all musical object which has been used for thousands of years and people who used got it in legacy from their Father or one of their family members.

Differences

Differences here are, Sosso Bala is a mysterious art object, the world's oldest balafon existence since 13th century kept in Nyagassola town on the border between Guinea and Mali, and it's also one of the property of the king Sumaoro Kanté, who received this object as a gift from an invisible powerful people.

This object was the origin of his power because it used to reveal him everything about his opponents and enemies, but after the battle of Kirina opposing the Sosso Empire and the Mali Empire this mysterious art object became the property of Sunjata Keita King of Mali Empire which was the symbol of their freedom.

So by seeing those two art objects similarities and differences we can say that through the exchange of culture we can all benefit from each other the power of our art object by making their differences an abilities a strong way to share our knowledge.

Conclusion

It will be the recap without repeating, demonstrate how the two objects of each country are similar or different by using the main point, saying why it's matter in order to develop their respective countries according to their different position in art History. In sum up the comparative study will help get the similarities and differences between art objects in order to either use their similarities to develop the poorest one nor transforming their differences into abilities to each one of them, knowing more about their art and culture which means developing yours by using theirs reciprocally. This project is going to generate the modernization to the my fellow young people working in our cultural, studying historical art educates us about how people saw themselves and their surroundings, as well as how they wanted to present it to others. Because the act of generating art is one of humanity's most pervasive acts, art history provides a mechanism through which we might understand our human past and its link to our present.

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